

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDY OF MESO SCALE ADHESIVE BONDABLE PULTRUSIONS

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SUMMARY

The paper describes the experimental and numerical approach to study the moulding and adhesive bonding of small (meso) laminates, typically 10x10x1mm. These represent layers of pultruded composite of glass fibre and vinyl ester resin. The aim of the study is to optimise the architecture of these layers and understand the failure at GFRP interfaces in relation to bonding for structural applications.

Keywords: Pultrusion, Moulding, Delamination, Adhesive joint, Marine structure

INTRODUCTION

The potential of GFRP glass/vinyl ester pultrusions (sections) in civil and marine structures can be increased significantly if the structural efficiency of the adhesive joint for these sections is increased. The efficient methods of joining composite structures are either adhesively bonding or mechanically fastened [1]. The tensile strength capacity of mechanical fastened joint is 50% due to local stress concentration caused by fasteners. In comparison, tensile strength capacity of adhesively bonded joint has the potential to reach in excess of 80% [2]. Currently the capacity of double lap shear (DLS) joint to that of the adherend/pultrusion is hardly reaching 40%. The improvement of structural efficiency of the joint depends on the properties of adherends including resin, fabric and its architecture, adhesive type, joint geometry and surface preparation [3]. This also depends on bonding surface details which might be represented at a meso-scale level. Figure 1 shows schematics which represent models for a DLS joint and its meso-scale component, showing peel stresses through material thickness. The meso model accounts for stress variation through-thickness, more accurately and hence the ability to predict how and why the material failed can be better understood.

Figure 1. The concept of meso-modelling

Pultrusion is one of the few continuous processes for composite manufacture, which could potentially make it one of the cheapest, for weight-critical structures e.g. a ship deck. A pultruded section may often contain uni-directional (UD) reinforcements (rovings) at the centre, with the skin of random/continuous strand (CSM) mats as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Design concept of pultrusion section with layers details.

Narrow strips may be based entirely on UD reinforcements but there are limited to simple sections that are not suitable for structural applications. A possible replacement for the skin mat, in wider sections e.g. channels or planks could be a stitched or woven (0/90) mats. These could enhance stiffness and strength better than the random ones. While pultrusion design allows good side-by-side joints, it is more difficult to achieve this for end-to-end connection and therefore, bolted joints are often considered. The introduction of holes in the composite leads to high stress concentrations and to counteract this, thicker (and heavier) walls will be needed. The architecture of fabric layers is important for adhesion and this is often neglected and this often dictated by the requirement to balance the stiffness and strength in longitudinal and transverse directions of the pultruded sections.

In testing DLS joints, it is quite difficult to catch the initial failure and propagation at meso scale, because it occurs in quick and brittle manner. Failure initiation has been predicted by numerical analysis and visual inspection of fractured specimens. Examinations of fractured specimens and their surfaces showed that in most of the tests, failure initiated by a transverse crack from the joint edge near the adhesive tip and this is followed by shear cracking of few filaments deep or might be initiated at the interlaminar between fabric and roving interface into the overlap region of composite. The main reasons for such a failure are the limitations of the pultrusion materials and moulding process. For a given matrix resin, the fabric architecture, fillers and mould release agent can make a considerable difference to adhesion [4]. It is currently unreasonable to expect better than 38% structural efficiency for basic design DLS joints based on commercial GFRP pultrusion. This has been improved to over 50% by introducing a low viscosity resin coating to the bonding surface prior to bonding. The low viscosity resin provides good micro-flow on the surface, resulting in a better wettability between the adhesive and the adherend [5].

Considerable research has been undertaken in recent years to improve on the strength of adhesive joints for pultrusions. Herakovich et al. [6] examined the fibre spacing and resin rich areas in pultruded composites. They conclude that significant strength reduction due to uneven fibre distribution and spacing between them. Pultruded composite shows a non linear response during loading, which is due to nature of different materials lay-up but the major impact is due to the voids and micro defects. Voids contents are relatively high in pultruded composite as compared to the composite made up by another method. Wang et al [7] studied the tensile behaviour of I-section beam pultruded structure. They showed considerable numbers of voids at different location of I-beam effect its strength in both longitudinal and transverse direction. Mat layer consisted of chopped strand mat (CSM) and a woven or stitched mat 0°/90°. Keller et al [8] pointed out that the peel and shear strength is slightly influenced by the number of outer mat layers. Adams et al. [3] pointed out that the

cracks are propagated easily though the thickness direction between the mat layers, where there is little reinforcement. Final failure occurs when the surface layer delaminates from the adherend in the overlap region through a combined peel and shear stresses including the transverse shear in the composite. Keller et al. [9] reported that joint failure was initiated by the combination of through thickness peel and shear stresses in the adhesive fillet and in the outer fibre mat layers of the adherend below the joint edges. Failure propagation always occurred by delamination in the mat region. Keller used new shear-tensile interaction (STI) testing device for combined shear and tensile loadings and introduced the shear-tensile interaction failure criterion for measuring the interlaminar stresses.

$$Q(\sigma_z, \tau_{xz}) = \left(\frac{\sigma_z}{\sigma_{z,U}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{xz}}{\tau_{xz,U}} \right)^2 = 1$$

Several analytical models are available in the literature. Some of them are based on beam theory. Volkerson [10] pointed out shear stress distributions in an adhesive single lap joint in tension by neglecting the bending effect of adherends. Hart-Smith [11] proposed a lap joint analysis and accommodates non linear adhesive material characteristics in Volkerson's shear lap analysis. Golland and Reissner [12] presented a single lap joint analysis as a cylindrically bent plate joined by elastic adhesive, modelling both bending and stretching of the adherends.

EXPERIMENTS SET-UP

Materials and properties

The main constituent materials used for the laminates are glass rovings and vinyl ester resin. Other materials used are epoxy coating, Araldite 2015 epoxy adhesive and aluminium. The latter is used to sandwich the laminates for mechanical testing. The properties of these materials are listed in Tables 1 and 2. These include data from manufacturers, mechanical testing and calculation methods.

Table 1. Properties of constituent materials

Property	Glass Fibre	Vinyl ester Resin	Araldite 2015	Aluminum	Coating resin
Young's modulus [GPa]	72	3	2	75	3
Poisson's ratio	0.2	0.36	0.36	0.37	0.37
Tensile strength [MPa]		90	40	180	50

Table 2. Material properties of GFRP laminate

Property	
E ₁ (GPa)	47.9
E ₂ = E ₃ (GPa)	10.7
G ₁₂ = G ₁₃ (GPa)	3.30
G ₂₃ (GPa)	4
ν ₁₂ = ν ₁₃	0.26
ν ₂₃	0.34
X (MPa)*	600
Y (MPa)**	20

* Longitudinal strength ** Transverse strength

Calculations for the properties of the GFRP were based on the volume fractions of the constituents. The fibre and matrix content were determined by the weight method. "Rule of mixtures" [13] was used to calculate properties in longitudinal direction of the fibre while Tsai and Hahn stress partitioning parameter [14] was used to estimate the properties in the transverse directions. In addition, standard mechanical test methods were used to determine the longitudinal and transverse strength of the UD/GFRP specimens.

Details of laminates

The meso laminates consist of glass rovings, vinyl ester resin, internal mould release agent and calcium based filler powder. Three processes were considered for the production, including moulding, coating and bonding of the laminates. These were carried out according to the manufacturer recommendations; include mixing of resin, its hardening and initiating components and organisation of the glass rovings (4800 Tex and 3600 Tex).

The moulding was developed to produce 20x20 mm, up to 1.4 mm thick flat composite laminates. These represent surface layers within critical locations of DLS joints. Figure 3 shows the details of the multi-layered laminates and their designations. LT and LL laminates refer to arrangement of fabric at 0/90 and 0/0 sequences, respectively. The fabric arrangement in the stitched laminate is similar to the LT but with a smaller roving size. The woven laminate is represented by alternate layers of mixed 0/90 sequence. The moulding and coating processes of the laminates are described below.

Figure 3. Meso-laminates with epoxy coating.

Production of laminates

E-glass was supplied by Formax (UK) Limited in tow (roving) forms and this was firstly cut into individual rovings each 100mm in length. Four glass rovings were then bound together to make the cross section of 20 mm. For the resin, Altac 340 would normally be mixed with TRIG C (hardener) and TRIG 21 (initiator), internal mould release agent and calcium based filler powder. The filler power aims to improve the moulding process and mechanical properties of the composite. Hardener to resin ratio of (0.8:10) was used to impregnate the rovings.

Figure 4. Moulding jig showing a). impregnation b). clamping of impregnated rovings c). GFRP pultruded laminate before and after trimming.

However before this stage, some preparatory work had to be carried out on the mould itself. Firstly the jig was cleaned then PTFE sheet was cut to fit the mould to ensure a good mould release. Figure 4 shows aspects of the moulding process and laminates. The screw threads were tightened until the fibres were fully aligned. The tension applied had to be such that no fibre breakage occurred but also to allow for the resin volume to shrink and indeed this was a process which was difficult to control.

The specimens were then cut into size (20x20 mm) and the edges were smoothed. GFRP composites are extremely abrasive when machined [15] and so a special cutting tool was needed. The tool selected was the departmental parallel mounted diamond impregnated circular saw which was mounted in a horizontal axis milling machine.

The composite was cut to size (20x20 mm), and coated with the 0.1 mm low viscosity epoxy resin Araldite® AY103 as the resin, and HY 951 as the hardener prior to bonding. Using the electronic scales and by following the manufacturers guidelines for the resin/ hardener ratio, 10 g of resin was poured into a glass jar and then by using a syringe, 0.8 g of hardener was added. After vigorous shaking to ensure thorough mixing, the adhesive was left to stand for 20 minutes to allow the trapped air bubbles to dissipate and also to allow enough time for the gelation process to occur. Before the application of the coating, LOCTITE 7063 cleaning agent/solvent was used to clean the surfaces of the composites. Figure 5 shows the effect of the surface coating before and after a GFRP specimen had been coated.

Adhesive bonding

This part explained the bonding of GFRP specimens to the aluminium substrates as shown in Figure 6. This is to produce the meso-scale shear and tensile adhesive joints/specimens. The production of the aluminium substrates and surfaces was of crucial point by two ways, firstly to ensure a good joint alignment, and secondly to minimise the edge effect of the laminates. The edge effect was reduced by applying PTFE to one surface of aluminium substrates (Figure 6). This resulted in bonding area of 10x10 mm - laminate dimensions were 20x20 mm. cleaning of aluminium prior to bonding is quite important because aluminium is a very oxidation-active material. This could affect adhesion. The specimens were lightly sand blasted prior to bonding and then cleaned with the solvent. The GFRP laminates were also cleaned before applying the epoxy adhesive Araldite® 2015 (Huntsman). The adhesive was mixed by means of a mixing nozzle attached to the cartridge and then by using specially designed tool, the adhesive was squeezed from the cartridges into a plastic mixing tray. To confirm the adhesive was well mixed, a wooden spatula was used to further mix the paste in the tray. The adhesive was then generously applied using a spatula to the GFRP specimens and the aluminium jig then joined together and inserted into the bonding jig.

Figure 5. Microscopic images of laminates
a). before b). after coating

Figure 6. Specimen bonding showing PTEF sheet to limit bond area to 10x10 mm

Figure 7 shows both tensile and shears specimens in the bonding jig before and after curing. The specimens were then cured in an oven for 1 hour at 85°C, after which time the oven was switched off and the door left slightly open to allow for a steady cooling rate.

Figure 7. Tensile and shear specimens (a) before and (b) after the curing.

Mechanical testing

- Several specimens were tested under monotonic tensile loading with Zwick/Roell tensile testing machine at a constant cross head speed of 0.5 mm/min at ambient temperature. Figure 8 shows the experimental set-up and load-displacement curves for shear specimens. The displacement was measured by external extensometer along the joint overlap.

Figure 8 Testing of bonded joints - (a) shear specimen during testing (b) load-displacement curves of Stitched shear specimens and (c) configurations of tensile and shear specimens.

The effect of resin coating was also tested and Figure 9 shows the variation in load-displacement between coated and uncoated joints. This clearly indicates the effectiveness of the low viscosity coating in increasing wettability and adhesion resulting in higher strength as well as strain to failure. The summary of results are given in Table 3 which shows average failure load from three test results for the shear and tensile specimens. The following remarks can be made:-

- failure load for LL shear joint is about 10% higher than LT shear joint
- failure load for Stitched shear joint is about 18% higher than Woven shear joint
- failure load for Stitched shear joint is about 8% higher than LL shear joint
- failure loads for LL and TL tensile joints the same. Both cases load is perpendicular to the roving (filaments)
- failure load of Stitched tensile joint is 29% higher than LL tensile joint
- failure load for Stitched tensile joint is about 63% higher than Woven tensile joint.

Table 3. Test result of meso scale specimens

Load / Type	Load	Standard Deviation	Filler	Fibre Content (% wt)	
	(kN)	(kN)			
Shear	LL	2.4	0.28	No	70
	LT	2.2	0.34	No	70
	Stitched	2.6	0.08	Yes	70
	Woven	2.2	0.27	Yes	70
Tensile	LL	1.4	—	No	70
	LT	1.4	—	No	70
	Stitched	1.8	0.17	Yes	70
	Woven	1.1	0.09	Yes	70

Figure 9. Variation in load-displacement of bonded laminates uncoated and coated.

Joint failure examination

The joints were carefully designed to ensure that failure initiates at specific locations, nearer the edge of the joints. However, it is extremely difficult to determine the exact locus of failure because this happened in a brittle and sudden manner. In the LL or LT shear joints, failure could have initiated as a crack from the transverse/peel stresses at the joint edge near adhesive tip. This would then be followed by shear cracking of few filaments deeper from the surface. Another possibility is that failure could initiate at interlaminar position between the two fabric layers. Fractured surfaces of laminates are shown in Figure 10 for tensile and shear specimens. The figure also shows closer images of roving regions before and after failure. Highlighted areas include, green for voids, red for resin rich areas, black for other defects. The yellow circle and line indicate failure. Fibre spacing and uneven distribution, resin rich areas and voids, micro defects in pultruded composites are the main cause of premature failure. Voids contents are relatively high in pultruded composite as compared to the composite made up by other methods [7].

Figure 10. Aspects of joint and surface failure - (a) fractured LL tensile specimen (b) fracture of LT shear specimen (c) defects in roving/laminate before failure (d) fracture of roving.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

This FEA modelling was mainly used to understand failure and behaviour the meso-scale adhesive bonded LL models, loaded in shear and tensile modes. Therefore, stress FEA models were constructed in Abaqus/CAE Version 6.7-1 which include modelling of the multi-through thickness materials i.e. adhesive, coating resin, matrix resin, and impregnated roving, as shown in Figure 11. The details of the tensile model are the same except for loading and boundary conditions. The 2-D models used 8-node plane strain quadrilateral, reduced integration element type CPE8R. Each node has two degrees of freedom in x and y direction. Analysis was made on both plane stress and plane

strain conditions. A small difference was found for the peel stresses in laminate. However, plane strain condition was selected for rest of the analysis based on thin laminate used in this study and failure load was applied to the models.

Figure 11. Schematic of shear specimen showing the multi layers within the LL laminate.

Material properties were based on the data from Tables 1 and 2, including the orthotropic properties of the GFRP. Elastic-full plastic properties were considered for the adhesive with elastic properties for the brittle vinyl ester and epoxy resins. The adhesive bondline thickness was modelled at 0.2 mm and 0.1 mm was considered for coating resin. The connection between resin, coating, adhesive and composite was perfectly bonded. The adhesive was divided into four elements and the resin into two elements to allow for determination of through thickness stresses. The critical stresses in the adhesive are shear and peel. Mesh sizing is quite important in FEA and the optimisation was obtained when no significant difference feel in load-displacement curve with progressive load.

The distributions of shear and peel stresses through the thickness of laminate are shown in Figure 12, for the shear model/joint. Although the stresses are high near the top of the laminate and coating, the nature of the multi-layer materials suggests two critical locations for failure initiation. These are (i) laminate top surface; say within the top 0.1 mm just below the epoxy coating and (ii) interlaminar location at about 0.6 mm below the surface, i.e. at the matrix resin between the two composite layers. Perhaps more critically are the peel/transverse stresses at the surface which are concentrated at the edge. Although interlaminar failure was observed in some specimens, fibre tear (delamination) failure is more dominant

Figure 12. FEA LL shear model– (a) through thickness location (b) stresses distribution along AA

Figure 13 shows the LL shear model and relevant stresses distributions along the joint at surface level. Again, the focus here is on the peel within the interfaces of the adhesive and composite, at the right-

hand side of the joint, at the interface between the adhesive and laminate. The peel stresses in composite is about 24 MPa.

Figure 13. FEA LL shear model - (a) critical edge location, (b) stresses distributions along adhesive and laminate surface.

The behaviour and failure stresses of the FEA tensile model are shown in Figure 14. Again the critical peel stresses are at the edge of the joint. The figure shows that the maximum peel in the composite surface is just over 16 MPa, which is considerably lower than that in the shear model. The question here; does the shear stress component of the shear model leads to reducing the effect of the peel component? This will be discussed further in the following section.

DISCUSSION

The “pseudo-pultrusion” moulding method used in this study was proven to be an effective tool to produce small laminates. This enabled the production and study of samples with various fabric and materials arrangement. However, results on Table 3 suggest that more moulding parameters need to be considered. The experimental results showed the effectiveness of using stitched fabric which gave higher strength than woven fabric in shear and in tension. This makes a good substitution for CSM (continuous strand mat) widely used as a top surface layer. The Stitched laminate is somewhat similar to the LT one; the difference is that the latter uses a thicker roving (Tex). LL gives higher strength than LT but again the strength of LL would be higher should a thinner roving was used. In addition the LL laminates gave high scatter. Otherwise it has the potential the higher individual strength (Figure 9).

The initial results of the experimental programme have confirmed that there is a weakness in the vinyl ester resin based pultruded material. The surface glass rovings of the laminate were delaminating at filaments level, resulting in joint failure at a relatively low load in comparison with the tensile capacity of the loaded adherend. Coating of the adherend with low viscosity epoxy resin gave significant improvement (Figure 9). Examination of fractured specimens showed that failure is taking place below the epoxy coating layer, initiated by a transverse delamination from the right edge of the joint and this is followed by shear/tensile delamination of few filaments deep. This might also be initiated at the interlaminar between fabric roving layers which makes shear-tensile interaction failure criterion for measuring the interlaminar stresses applicable. Although most joints have failed at the composite just below the surface, initiating at the localised interfaces, the composite stresses at the surface may be taken as a good indicator of the sub surface stresses in the composite.

Figure 14. FEA LL tensile model – (a) critical location (b) stresses distributions along adhesive and laminate surface.

The FEA modelling demonstrated the importance of having detailed through-thickness layers which enabled a better understanding of failure and behaviour bonded pultrusions. In a recent related work [16], a good agreement was found between the macro and meso FEA models, with respect to composite peel stresses at composite surface. The peel stress value was about 24 MPa. This stress values is within the range of transverse strength of the composite (Table 2). Furthermore, the level of scatter in the experimental results (standard deviation) is quite large for the meso-specimens and this was used as the average failure load, contributing further to the scatter. The FEA is limited here to the LL models but further correlations are needed for other models. This requires further numerical and experimental work.

The difference in peel stresses between FEA shear and tensile models is about 40% and this requires careful explanations. Among the possibilities/reasons this are:-

- (i) the stresses are picked at a prescribed distance from point of singularity which may not be the same for tensile and shear
- (ii) the shear model has a combined shear and peel stresses. This may result in reducing the effect of peel component while the tensile one is dominated by peel only
- (iii) the tensile specimens are generally more sensitive to testing, moulding and bonding parameters than the shear ones, and hence the former didn't realise it's potential for higher failure load.

Finally, because of the complex nature of the pultruded composite and materials, the assessment and analysis require the modelling the approach to be extended to micro-scale model. In fact the microscopic examinations of the pultruded composite in Figure 10 explain nature of the problem, which need to be understood at a filament level.

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